

Laser Surface Texturing on Biomedical Implants

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Abstract—One of the new technologies for producing a texture or pattern on a work surface is laser surface texturing (LST). It is a practical way to add texture to a work area. The use of various lasers to create textures on the surface of work materials is documented in the literature. LST has recently demonstrated incredible potential in the area of biological applications. The LST technique has significantly increased the biomaterial's effectiveness. An extensive analysis of laser surface texturing for biomedical applications is presented in this research. A detailed analysis of LST's impact on significant biomaterials revealed that it has a tremendous potential for surface modification of biomaterials and can be used in biomedical applications.

Keywords— *laser micromachining, surface texturing, surface roughness, biomedical engineering.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In essence, surface texturing is a technique for creating a specific pattern or texture on a work surface. It is a useful technique for altering the surface of a material to improve its tribological characteristics, such as load capacity, wear resistance, and coefficient of friction. Among all texturing techniques, laser surface texturing (LST) has gained popularity among researchers for its great efficiency, superb controllability, environment-friendliness, and accuracy. Numerous engineering applications in the biomedical, tribology, and coating fields have successfully exploited this technique. Dimple and microgroove of varied sizes and forms are two examples of the textured patterns. An extensive analysis of LST on numerous biomedical applications is presented in this publication. Worldwide, basic research is being done on different types and shapes of surface texturing for tribological applications. Texturing methods such as machining, etching, and laser texturing are used in these studies. Laser surface texturing (LST) appears to give the most promising idea among the various patterning techniques. This is because of the laser's incredibly quick processing times, environmental friendliness, and superb control over texture size and shape, which enables the implementation of the best designs. It has been proven that using laser surface texturing is an efficient way to modify and regulate surfaces' physicochemical and micro-topographic characteristics.

Modern magnetic storage devices frequently have textured surfaces, and surface texturing is also thought of as a way to combat adhesion. Furthermore, it was convincingly demonstrated that in additive manufacturing, surface texturing was more crucial than traditional machining. Additionally, more surface texturing work had been done, primarily on Ti-6Al-4V.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The best method that is going to belong to creating textures happened to be identified after reviewing several research articles. An existing variety that belongs to patterns happen to be formed by changing an existing number that belongs to crucial laser settings. Many studies have been attempting to surface micro-texture different hatching patterns on top of metals as well as study its surface properties. Certain authors utilized nanosecond laser ablation to create an existing polymeric structured small as well as medium enterprises texture on top of an existing plate.

Some author used to use an existing texture to improve the biological properties that belongs to the polymers without affecting their mechanical qualities. this means, implant fibrosis has the ability exist as a effectively minimized, encouraging

tissue integration. The results reported inside of the overall literature happen to be highly promising, showing the useful utility that belongs to 1st to resolve some that belongs to the difficulties that belongs to these materials inside of the field that belongs to biomedical implants.

III. METHODOLOGY

I. Objectives

- Using the Taguchi method to vary parameters and generate the work pieces accordingly.
- To find the effect of variation of various parameters of a LASER machine like Power, Scan speed, Frequency on the textured surface.
- To find the interrelation between these parameters and hatch/groove width and Roughness.
- Generating graphs to obtain the relation between variation of laser parameters width and roughness.

II. Tools and Technology

FIGURE 1.Nanosecond pulse LASER machine

FIGURE 2.Rapid I-vision microscope

Details of LASER machine used

- Nanosecond pulse laser machine
- Mode of Operation- Pulsed
- Output Power- 30.5 ± 2.0 W
- Polarization-Random
- Output Power Adjustment-10-100%
- Pulse Energy-1.0 mJ (Nominal)
- Pulse Width- 100 ± 20 ns
- Operating Ambient Temperature-0 to 42°C
- DC Supply Voltage-23 – 25 VDC
- FWHM at the lowest PRR and full rated power.

C. *Material Selection*

The plates chosen for the experiments are made of Titanium Alloy (Ti6Al4V) Grade 5. Some important properties of the material used are given in Table 1.

Table 1

N Property	Value	Unit
Atomic Volume (avg.)	0.01	m ³ /km
Density	4.5	mg/m ³
Bulk Modulus	111	GPa
Hardness	70	MPa
Latent Heat (Fusion)	0.72	kJ/kg
Melting Point	1941	K
Specific Heat	0.93	J/kgK
Thermal Conductivity	7.5	W/mK
Thermal Expansion	8.8	10 ⁻⁶ /K

D. *Constant Parameters*

Material: Titanium Alloy (Ti6Al4V) Grade 5

- Focal length: 32.1 cm
- Loop count: 1
- Size of Experiment: 8mm *8 mm
- Distance between hatches: 150µm
- Number of hatches per experiment: 54
- Hatching Pattern: Straight horizontal lines

E. Variable Parameters

Table 2

Parameter No.	Variable	Values
1	Power (W)	0.3
		1.5
		7.5
		15
		20
2	Scan Speed (mm/s)	10
		50
		100
		200
		300
3	Frequency (kHz)	60
		70
		80
		90
		100

IV. Experiments

1. Selective Laser Melting and Microscopic measurements for Groove Width

FIGURE 3: Microscopic images of LASER texturedTiAl4V Grade 5

Titanium Alloy (Ti6Al4V) Grade 5 plates of size 20mm * 20mm were chosen for performing the experiments. On EzCAD software, a square of size 8 mm * 8 mm was designed with horizontal line hatching. The distance between the lines was kept 150µm. The thickness of the titanium plate was 1 mm. On one side we had 4 experiments on each side.

2. *Roughness Measurements by using Surface Finish Tester*

The surface texture or surface roughness of a substance can be quickly and precisely determined with a roughness tester. A roughness tester displays both the measured mean roughness value (Ra) and roughness depth (Rz) in micrometers or microns (μm). Applying a roughness filter to a surface allows you to measure its roughness. Different roughness filters should be used, according to various international standards and surface texture or surface finish demands.

Results and Discussions

FIGURE 4. Variation of Width (mm)

As from the graph above, the hatch width was observed with rise power from 1% to 70%. The width was first increased and was maximum at 7.5W. Then the width decreased till 15W and the increased. So the result was when the scanning speed and frequency of the LASER is increased, the width increases and then decreases. And width increases with the increase in frequency.

FIGURE 5. Variation of Ra Values(μm)

As observed in the graph above, we can conclude that the Roughness of the hatches increases with a rise in power, while its trend is decreasing when scanning speed is increased and then it nearly remains constant. When the frequency is increased, the depth of the hatches first decreases from frequency 60kHz to 70kHz, and then it nearly remains constant.

APPLICATIONS

Our main aim for surface texturing techniques in biomedical applications is the enhancement of the cellular activity in the surface of the implant. In bone remodeling, textured surfaces show a higher surface area for integrating the implant with bone, via the osseointegration process.

The improvement of cellular activity on the implant's surface is our primary goal when using surface texturing techniques in biomedical applications. In the remodeling of bone, textured surfaces exhibit a greater surface area for the osseointegration process, which integrates the implant with bone. Additionally, textured surfaces will encourage the mechanical stability of implants by allowing for tissue in growth. As a result, this will also influence cell proliferation and improve cell adhesion, and it has been established that their impact on the gene expression for many cell types, particularly in humans, is significant.

FUTURE SCOPE

There is a very broad future potential for LASER texturing on the surface of different metals. Surface texture has taken on significant importance in the design of medical devices. It gives the means to enhance an item's surface grip capabilities while also giving the means to improve an item's physical look. Additionally, surface texturing allows manufacturers to make medical devices that suck up less fluid and debris, mark implants for tracking, and add textures that promote implant acceptance. So it should come as no surprise that these medical producers are looking for more and more ways to increase their level of control over surface texture. Modern medical parts frequently use laser texturing, which is frequently the technology of choice.

Conclusion

The project successfully verified the shifting laser surface texturing method's effectiveness and accuracy. The surface roughness of Ti6Al4V (titanium alloy) was assessed using effective and dependable technology after a number of tests were carried out utilizing LST to create dimples that resembled squares. While maintaining other factors constant, the LASER Nanosecond Pulse laser machine's parameters were changed, and their effects on the width and roughness of the laser hatches were noted. Variations in the LASER machine's power, frequency, and scanning speed were also made, and variations in width and roughness were noticed. We came to the conclusion that the width of the hatches initially rises with an increase in power up to 7.5W, then falls until, and finally rises. The width grows subsequently lowers as the LASER's scanning speed and frequency are raised. And as frequency rises, width also does as well.

After observing the variance in roughness values, we came to the conclusion that the roughness of the hatches rises with power while trending downward as scanning speed is raised before nearly being constant. The depth of the hatches reduces from frequency 60kHz to 70kHz as the frequency is raised, then practically stays constant after that.

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